

Modules in Critical Reading for Third Year and Fourth Year High School Students (Graduate School, Daniel B. Peña Memorial College Foundation, Inc. March 1996)

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Abstract:- A developmental research on modules in critical reading for third year and fourth year students was conducted at the Tabaco National High School for School Year 1995-1996. Five modules for each year level were prepared for the development and further enhancement of the third year and fourth year students' critical reading skills. The five modules for the third year are; Module 1 Making Inferences, Module 2 Distinguishing Facts and Opinions, Module 3 Drawing Conclusions, Module 4 Identifying Author's Mood, Purpose and Tone, Module 5 Evaluating Values Presented. For the fourth year, the five modules are; Module 1 Making Inferences, Module 2 Distinguishing Facts and Opinions, Module 3 Identifying Author's purpose, Technique, Style and Audience, Module 4 Drawing Conclusions and Forming Judgements, and Module 5 Recognizing and Analyzing Propaganda. These five critical reading skills were based on the skills suggested in the Desired Learning Competencies (DLC) for each year level. In the preparation of the modules, the researchers carefully selected passages, poems, excerpts of stories from reference books, magazines, newspapers and even chosen speeches. A few of the passages were original. The materials were chosen in terms of their interest factor, ability level of the students and the suitability of the objectives to the materials. The prepared modules were submitted to a panel of jurors, composed of a regional supervisor, a department head, reading specialists, key teachers and subject teachers. Sample modules were also given to selected students to test the modules readability and comprehensibility before the try-out. The pretest prepared by the researchers set the baseline. The result revealed that the students were fairly competent in critical reading skills. Analysis of data concentrated on the means, standard deviation, mean performance levels, t-test of difference between correlated means and analysis of variance (ANOVA) to determine the reliability and validity of the modules in relation to the learners' abilities. Decisions on the hypotheses were pegged at 5 percent level of significance. Findings revealed significant improvement in the critical reading skills of both the third year and the fourth year as reflected by a marked increase in the post-test mean gains of 12.67 for the third year and 12.43 for the fourth year. The T-test of the difference between the means of the pre-test and the post-test of 5.21, 6.70, 7.95 for high ability group, average ability group and the low ability group in the fourth year respectively showed

significant changes in the students' critical reading performance in the post-test in relation to the pre-test. From these findings, it can be concluded that the modular instruction developed the critical reading skills of the students. The analysis of variance showed no significant differences in the three ability groups in the fourth year. The difference was only significant between the High Ability Group and the Low Ability Group in the third year. It was also noted that the average ability group and the low ability group in the third year while the average ability group and the high ability group got higher mean gains than that of the low ability group in the fourth year. In conclusion, the modules are found to be most beneficial to the average ability group for the fourth year and the low and average ability groups for the third year. The coefficients of correlation between the pre-test and the post-test results for the third year were 0.59 for the High Ability Group, 0.63 for the Average Ability Group and 0.69 for the Low Ability Group. For the fourth year, the computed coefficients of correlation were 0.36, 0.69 and 0.73 for the High Ability Group, average ability group and 0.69 for the Low Ability Group. For the Fourth Year, the computed coefficients of correlation were 0.36, 0.69, and 0.73 for the High Ability Group, Average Ability Group and the Low Ability Group. These coefficients of correlation for both the third year and fourth year showed positive significant correlations. Hence, the modules are found to be valid and reliable. Finally, the researchers recommend further refinement and try-out of the modules under other research settings, and the preparation of similar materials in other subject areas to complement and supplement conventional classroom instruction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Today, a vision of tomorrow dominates our national life. The vision is a set of goals which reflected the heightening national desire for excellence. An increasing concern about the quality of human life for the Filipino people. Quality education for every Filipino is a constitutional mandate and everybody's concern. Section 1 of article XIV of the Philippine Constitution states that the "State shall protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels and shall take appropriate steps to make such education accessible to all." This provision is echoed by another provision in Batas Pambansa

Blg. 232 (The Education Act of 1982). Section 3 of chapter 3 specifically states that *“The state shall promote the right of every individual to relevant quality education, regardless of sex, age, creed, socio-economic status, origin, political or other affiliation. The state shall therefore promote and maintain equality of access to education as well as the enjoyment of the benefits of education by all its citizens”*. Educators, legislators, parents, and laymen alike aver that quality education is a foundation of a strongly developed country. And that a nation’s strength is determined by the quality of education it provides its citizenry. The Philippine educational system, however, is confronted by a continuing problem of poor academic performance of pupils and students. Results of test and research studies have proven this and reported that the mean percentages in almost all the learning areas obtained by our pupils and students in the NEAT and NSAT, respectively were below the 75 percent criterion for mastery level. In developing reading skills especially, the critical reading skills, the teacher should make every effort to introduce new skills and abilities in reading in a gradual manner. By gradual development with relatively small and easy steps, the student learns a whole set. This requirement is met by individualized instruction through programmed reading materials, self-learning kits or learning modules. This learning materials which cater to the varying levels of abilities, interest and needs of students are not always available and many of the teachers in the field express lack of competence in developing these materials. Thus, the writers hope that the modules which will be presented and intended to develop specific critical reading skills will help ease the problem on the paucity of instructional materials in reading in the field. Hence, this research study. The setting of the study was conducted in Tabaco National High School where the try-out modules prepared in this research. The school is one of the biggest national high schools in the Division of Albay.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study is based on the theory propounded by Gray which stated, “each child, youth and adult lives in, react to and is directed by the ideas, values, feelings and information acquired in the process of receptive communication. Life is continuous, but its reality exists only in each act of interacting with the factors operating in the external environment.” He further opines that “students grow in power of critical evaluation as they grow in maturity and that this growth may be accelerated by purposeful guidance. As one’s capacity matures, as one’s ability to manipulate verbal symbols and grasp language relationship grows, as one acquires new and varied experiences, his potentiality for interpretive and critical reading also increases. This theory is supported by Gregorio when he stressed that learning is an individual process. Each particular pupils / student is unique and a distinct personality. And that learning must proceed in terms of the learner’s own purpose, abilities, aptitudes, interests, and needs.

III. OPERATIONAL FRAMEWORK

Reading experts agreed that reading is a developmental task. Each developmental task must be achieved in proper sequence If the learner is to be successful with later task. The developmental sequence has important implications to teaching particularly in teaching reading and/or developing critical reading skills. Bond and Wagner claim that the most effective means of developing so complex an ability or skill as reading is through programmed and individualized instruction using self-learning kits or modules. The module as an instructional system could be a replacement of conventional teaching, a part of teaching, a research technique in evaluating programs considered as teaching method. It is presented routes to the heart of instruction and simultaneously allowing him to interact or respond actively in the process. The immediate feedback scheme informs the learner to proceed or refer to another item of information depending on the correctness of his answers. One of the thrusts of the DECS is to raise the over-all quality of basic education. And quality education requires measures which would guarantee a more reliable, valid and integrated learning programs that are based on research. Thus, the construction of instructional materials like the modules using the developmental approach can be a worthwhile contribution along this effort of developing / improving the critical reading skills of students.

IV. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

According to Fitrawati (2023), Content and Language Integrated Learning CLIL, a system for teaching and learning information through a foreign language, has emerged as a potential tool for developing critical reading material and building students’ analytical thinking and reasoning abilities in higher education. Only a few studies have concentrated on creating and implementing CLIL-based techniques in higher education, despite the fact that many have looked at the production of critical reading teaching materials. As a result, his paper investigates how English students and instructors feel about using interactive multimedia and CLIL-based ideas to create critical reading materials for higher education.

Sala (2023) conducted a study on the promotion of critical reading through the digital environment: A study on the virtual epitexts used to promote children’s picture books. He stated that the most current reading research studies depict a new cultural environment in which analog and digital reading coexist and influence what is read, either by changing how reading is done or by encouraging reading. In this context, UNESCO and the curricular frameworks built on its ideas highlight how crucial it is to develop critical readers. The research offers a basically qualitative and interpretive documentary investigation of a sample of 836 virtual epitexts that advertise children's picture books in order to offer information for consideration on its subject.

The study of Balagua (2022), conducted a study to assess the Reading Modules Using Marungko Approach of Grade One Pupils in the Elementary Schools of Zambales, Philippines. The Marungko technique was used in the study to assess the efficacy of reading modules for grade one students in a few primary schools in Zambales, the Philippines, during the 2020–2021 academic year. According to the study, the student-participant is a normal male young preschooler whose parent works as a cleaner and lives in the central business district. In the initial pre-test evaluation, the students in the controlled and experimental groups had their levels of annoyance with word decoding, reading speed, and reading comprehension evaluated. In the second pre-test evaluation, the students who participated in the controlled and experimental groups were evaluated on their degree of annoyance with word decoding, reading speed, and reading comprehension. The controlled group's student participants were given a "Instructional level" evaluation for word decoding, sluggish reading speed, and annoyance with reading comprehension in the first post-test assessment. Independent word decoding, quick reading speed, and independent reading comprehension were evaluated for the experimental groups. The controlled group's student participants were given a "Instructional level" evaluation for word decoding, sluggish reading speed, and annoyance with reading comprehension in the second post-test assessment. Independent word decoding, average reading speed, and independent reading comprehension assessments were made for the experimental groups. The student participants' academic achievement was "Satisfactory". The researcher further suggested that the Marungko approach is a highly recommended intervention program for improving reading proficiency and academic performance; that the Marungko approach is the best intervention for word decoding, developing reading speed, and enhancing reading comprehension; that in-service training for teachers to become familiar with the application and integration of the Marungko Approach in the teaching and learning process is highly encouraged; and, in conclusion.

Septiyana (2021) Simply stated that reading is the act of comprehending and learning from a material. The meaning relationship that occurs inside the text to create a connection between its many elements is known as cohesion. Students who comprehend cohesiveness will read with greater comprehension. Furthermore, he aimed in his research the desire to demonstrate a link between students' reading comprehension and coherence understanding. This study aims to analyze and determine the relationship between the reading comprehension and coherence of EFL learners. The analysis of the data reveals that the correlation between cohesion understanding and reading comprehension is 0.728, and that the critical value of r Product Moment for the 5% level is 0.361 and for the 1% level is 0.463. These values were determined by using the Product Moment table and df 30. The information demonstrated that r observed exceeds r table. Therefore, it can be concluded that, among fourth semester students at the English education department of the State Islamic Institute of Metro in the academic year 2019/2020, there is a favorable and substantial association

between the students' coherence understanding and reading comprehension.

Oakhill (2019) conducted a study Reading Comprehension and Reading Comprehension Difficulties. He stressed that based to The Simple View of Reading, word reading and language understanding are two major components of reading comprehension. In addition to word reading abilities, this chapter examines the numerous other characteristics that have a direct influence on language understanding and reading comprehension. We investigate in depth the concepts of vocabulary, inference, background knowledge, comprehension monitoring, and text structure knowledge. The relationship between these elements and reading comprehension is discussed, as well as how to best help readers who have trouble understanding read aloud.

According to Isik (2023) the ability to communicate effectively through language has a big impact on how people think, perceive their environment, and express themselves. Language acquisition begins with hearing in the womb. When a child first opens his eyes to the universe, he discovers the through combining what he hears and observes, he learns things. The youngster improves his speech by using the words he has previously learned abilities. Reading and writing abilities are added to a child's listening and speaking abilities when they start school. the vital communication abilities that develop during infancy.

Xolmatovna (2023) in his article focuses on fundamental facts about how to improve reading comprehension to ensure one can read and learn at the same time. The most frequent issue faced by English language learners is their inability to comprehend the texts they are reading. Thus, the question of how to enhance students' reading abilities is becoming more and more important. In order to help English language learners, become more proficient readers, the study has examined several basic reading techniques and offered some recommendations for their future development.

The study of Shuxratillayevna (2023) is an application of action research to a group of 14 students taking an integrated skills course at the intermediate level. Would reading techniques benefit my pupils' studies of reading comprehension? is the primary research question. The study's findings show that pupils significantly improved after receiving instruction in reading skills. In his statement, the development of pupil comprehension depends critically on the teaching of reading methods. Many educators, however, lack a strong basis for introducing these reading comprehension techniques. As a result, teachers must be ready to teach their pupils these methods and to build successful comprehension tactics. As a result, the goal of this study is to examine the most successful reading techniques for language classrooms.

V. RESEARCH METHODS AND DESIGN

This study employed the developmental research method following the fundamental steps suggested by Lysaught and Williams. Hence, this chapter is divided into

two main phases, namely: Phase I – Planning and Constructing of the Modules, and Phase II – Application and evaluation of the modules. Figure 2 shows the steps in module development.

VI. ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS THIRD YEAR

A. Means of the Pre-test and Post-Test

It was revealed that the High Ability Group (HAG) obtained a mean of 42.1 in the pre-test and 45.9 in the post-test with a mean gain of 3.8. It was also shown that the performance level of the High Ability Group was 84.2 percent in the Pre-Test and 91.8 percent in the Post-Test. This performance is above the criterion level set at 60 percent success for the fast learners. In addition, this presented a 31.8 percent increase in the mean percent. It was also reflected that the average Ability Group obtained a mean of 31.9 in the Pre-Test and 38 in the Post-Test. The mean gain was 6.1. It was revealed too, that the performance of level of the average ability group was 63.8 percent in the Pre-Test and 76 percent in the Post-Test. This performance is above the criterion set at 50 percent success for the average learners. The Low Ability Group got a mean of 28.8 in the Pre-Test and 35.8 in the Post-Test. The mean gain was 7.4 which was 1.3 higher than that of the High Ability Group and the average Ability Group. As a whole, the performance levels of both the average and Ability Group

and the Low Ability Group are above the level set by the DECS adopted by Region V (Bicol, Philippines) as well as the Division of Albay (Bicol). All the ability groups performed higher than the performance level set in the target objectives, that is 60 percent success for the High Ability Group, 50 percent for the Average Ability Group, and 40 percent for the Low Ability Group. For this reason, the criterion levels set for the attainment of the skills are achieved. Comparing the results of the results of the students' performance in the pre-test and post-test showed that the highest mean gain was obtained by the Low Ability Group followed by the Average Ability Group. As a whole, the three ability groups achieved a marked increase in the mean of the post-test, getting a grand mean of 39.9 over that of 34.27 in the pre-test and gain of 5.69 although there were differences in the obtained mean of the three groups.

B. Mean Gains in the Five Modules

To summarize, the Average Ability Group obtained a total mean of 31.9 in the pre-test and 38.0 in the post-test having a total mean gain of 6.1 which shows that the average ability group can learn more if they will be given varied teaching methods and devices. The Low Ability Group got the highest mean gain in the pre post – tests in all the five modules. Analyzing the mean obtained in the five modules it could be observed that the Low Ability Groups' lowest mean, 4.5 was on module 1 – Making Inferences, but increased to 6.5 in the post-test resulting to a mean gain of 2, the highest mean gain obtained in the five modules. This was followed by Module 2 – Identifying Facts and Opinions with a pre-test mean of 5.4 to 7.2 in the post-test, and a mean gain of 1.8. Module 4-Identifying author's purpose, mood and tone recorded a pre-test mean of 4.9 and post-test 6.5 having a mean gain of 1.6 Module 3 – Making conclusions had pre-test mean of 7.0 and 8.2 for Post-Test with gain of 1.2 Module 5 – Discriminating between positive and negative values had the lowest mean gain of .8. This could mean that this reading skill was the hardest for the Low Ability Group followed by Module 3 on Making Conclusions and Module 4 – Identifying author's purpose, mood and tone. To sum up, the Low Ability Group got the highest mean of 28.4 in the pre-test and 35.8 in the post-test with the mean gain of 7.4. This is a strong indication that the modules are most useful to the Low Ability Group.

C. A summary of the Means of Pre-Test and Post-Test in Each of the Modules

To sum up, the Highest obtained mean of 8.23 and 8.7 for the pre and post – tests, respectively, was in module 5 – discriminating between positive and negative values. This was followed in the descending order by Module 3 – Making Conclusions with the mean of 6.73 and 7.87; Module 2 – Distinguishing Facts and Opinions with the mean of 6.17 and 7.6 and lastly Module 4 – Identifying Author's mood, Purpose and Tone with the mean of 5.47 and 7.1 for the pre-test and post-test. As a whole, the great mean of 6.77 in the pre-test increased to a post-test mean of 7.98 mean attaining a grand mean gain of 1.15 shows that the students have improved their five critical reading skills through the use of the modules.

VII. FOURTH YEAR

A. Comparison between Post and Pre-Test

The result of pre-test in the pre-test conducted, the mean obtained were 31.2 for the High Ability Group, 21.8 for the Average Ability Group. The grand mean was 23.63, while the Results of Post-test revealed that post-test results recorded these means: 43 for the High Ability Group, 36.2 for the Average Ability Group and 29.0 for the Low Ability Group. A grand mean of 36.07 was obtained. These values were higher than the values obtained in the pre-test. Pre-test Results by Modules shows that pre-test means were 5.60 for module 1, 6.30 for module 2, 4.73 for module 3, 5.97 for Module 4, and 1.27 for Module 5. The total grand mean was 23.60, and for the post-test results by modules in the post-test the following means were recorded: Module 1 was 7.30, Module 2 was 7.60 Module 3 was 7.30 Module 4 was 7.13 and Module 5 got 6.37. the total grand mean was 36.07.

B. Comparison of Results by ability Levels

The high ability group recorded a pre-test mean of 31.2 and a 43.0 post-test mean with a mean gain of 11.8. Likewise, the average ability group obtained a pre-test mean of 21.8 which increased to 36.2 in the post-test. The mean gain was 14.4. The Low Ability Group registered a 17.9 mean in the pre-test, 29.0 in the post-test and a mean gain of 11.1. The Average Ability Group recorded the highest mean gain, followed by the high ability group and lastly by the low ability group. For the mean gains in the module in the High Ability Group, the module which registered the highest mean gain of 5.1 was module 5, on: Recognizing and analyzing propaganda. This was followed by Module 3 on: Identifying authors' purpose, audience, style or technique, module 1 on: Making inferences with mean gain of 1.7, Module 4 on: Drawing conclusions and making judgements with 1.3 mean gain and Module 2 on: Distinguishing facts from opinions with mean gain of 1.1 in that order. The grand mean was 2.36. Moreover, the average ability group obtained a much higher grand mean of 2.9. Getting the highest mean gain was Module 5 on: Recognizing and analyzing propaganda with a mean gain of 6.5. This was followed closely by Module 3 on: Identifying authors' purpose, audience, technique or style with 3.4 gain, Module 1 on: Making inferences with 2.4 gain, Module 2 on: Distinguishing facts from opinion and finally module 4 on: Drawing conclusions and making judgements with a minimal gain of 0.1. The grand mean of this group was 2.9. In the low ability group, the highest mean gain was obtained by module 5 on: Recognizing and analyzing propaganda with a mean gain of 3.7. this was followed by module 1 on: Making inferences with a mean gain of 2.1 and module 4 on: drawing conclusions and making judgements with also a 2.1 mean gain by Module 3 on: Identifying author's purpose, audience, style or technique with a gain of 1.7 and lastly by module 2 on: Distinguishing facts from opinions with a gain of 1.5.

C. Comparative Effectiveness of the Modules

In the Post-test the modules which obtained the highest means arranged in the descending order are Module 1 (X=7.67), Module 2 (X=7.60), module 3 (X=7.30), Module 4 (X=7.13), Module 5 (X=6.37). as to the comparison of results of the pre-test and post-test it was revealed that the computed t-ratios of 8.19 for the High Ability Group; 11.16 for the average ability group, and 17.90 for the low ability group were significant at 0.05 level of confidence for these values were greater than their corresponding tabular values at 2.262 for the High Ability Group, 1.29 for the Average Ability Group and 0.61 for the low ability group. For Comparison of Performance in the Ability Groups, the average ability group and the high ability seemed to be more benefited by the use of the modules as evidenced by the computed mean gains of 14.5 for the average ability group and 11.8 for the High ability group compared with 11.1 for the low ability group. However, in the analysis of the variance of means of the scores of the three groups in the post-test, the obtained value of 2.19 is not significant at 5 percent level of confidence.

D. Validity of Reliability of the Modules

The coefficients of correlation of 0.36, 0.62 and 0.73 for the high ability group between the pre-test scores and the post-test scores show that the prepared modules are reliable and valid.

VIII. CONCLUSION

With the above cited analysis and findings of this study, it was concluded that, There were significant improvements in the critical reading skills of students at 5 percent level of significance; The Average Group is the most benefited group by the modular instruction in the fourth year while the low and average ability groups were the ones most benefited in the third year; lastly, the prepared modules are reliable and valid for they develop the critical reading skills of the students in the try-out.

IX. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on these conclusions, it was recommended that there should have a further refinement of the modules through trying them out in another research setting of greater people; Pre-test should be given immediately after the opening of the classes so a real diagnosis of the students' ability levels will be obtained. Interest of the subjects in modules should be thoroughly instilled before the modular instruction. It is also recommended that modules as instruments in the study be revised or modified to make it more attractive to the above average group. For the benefit of the low ability group, some of the words or expressions should be simplified for their easy comprehension of the reading selections. Furthermore, the modules could be used as supplementary materials for enrichment purposes. Modular instruction in teaching could be used in all subject areas to complement and supplement conventional classroom teaching. Lastly, Out-of-School youths with acquired basic reading skills can make use of these modules for the enhancement of their critical reading.

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